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Mahmudhoja Behbudi - as a media activist

Annotation

This article discusses the efforts of the leading representative of the XX century, public figure, enlightener Jadid Mahmudhoja Behbudi in the field of the press, his articles, the ideas put forward in it.

Keywords

Behbudi, jadidism, article, newspaper, magazine, article, "Memories", "Good life umsotuhu", "Mirror", "Samarkand", controversy.

Born on January 20, 1875, in the village of Bakhshitepa near Samarkand, on the 10th of Dhu'l-Hijjah 1291 AH, Behbudi grew up in a very intelligent family and eventually became a mature representative of the Jadid movement.

Mahmudhoja Behbudi, who dreamed of seeing the people as a truly literate, intelligent, free, independent society, opened schools, libraries, and published newspapers and magazines at his own expense. He wrote a number of textbooks for the schools he opened, such as "Risolai tooli savod", "Risolai geography of Umrani", "Kitab ul-atfol", "Practice of Islam", "History of Islam", "Russian treatise of geography", "Muntahabi geography" and others. brochures are available.

From 1913, Behbudi was engaged in press work. In April, he started publishing the Samarkand newspaper. The newspaper is published in Turkish and Persian, twice a week, first two and then four pages. In 1913, Behbudi wrote in his newspaper "Samarkand" "Why do not they compliment?" publishes an article entitled [1]. The article was in the form of a complaint from a Turkestan penman who neglected the national service. Imagine, for the benefit of the people, from the Caspian Sea in the west, to Fulja and Kashgar in the east, from Kazakhstan in the north to Afghanistan in the south, a newspaper in the middle dialect of Turkestan could be established for the benefit of tens of millions of people. The author begins his grievances in Tashkent. For example, Behbudi writes, From Tashkent, not a single line, not a single thing came. "[2] Behbudi then began publishing the magazine Oyna on August 30. 'r It spread to the Caucasus, Tatarstan, Iran, Afghanistan, India and Turkey... It was a favorite magazine of the Jadids... "wrote Ziya Said [3].

Behbudi was actively involved in publishing during these years. AV Pyaskovsky reports that in his printing house he translated and published Fitrat's "Statement of the Indian Traveler" in Russian in 1913.

On May 29, 1914, Behbudi set out on a second voyage to the Arab world. He takes a train to Ashgabat via Bayramali. From Krasnovodsk by ferry to Baku. On June 2, he will travel to Mineralnye Vody-Kislovodsk-Pyatigorsk, Zheleznovodsk-Rostov-Odessa and enter Istanbul on June 8. After a short journey, he will return to Istanbul and make his way to Jerusalem by water on June 21st. He visited Beirut, Yofa, Khalil ar-Rahman, Port Said, and Damascus. These "Memories" are extremely important both in terms of enlightenment and literary-aesthetic. It is a unique example of the traditional historical-memoir genre in our literature of the early twentieth century.

Oyna magazine has made a great contribution to the dissemination of enlightenment and culture. It contains interesting articles and debates on the nation and its rights, history, language and literature, the state of the world. In particular, the issue of language has always been in the focus of the editor. Behbudi considered it necessary to know several languages for the development of the nation. The first issue of the magazine was published on August 13, 1913, with the headline "We need four languages, not two."

Behbudi paid great attention to literary criticism. After several centuries of silence after Navoi, he raised the issue of equality in the literature, emphasizing the peculiarities of the industry. The article was entitled "Criticism is Sorting" (No. 27, 1914). All of the author's articles on historical and scientific topics are written with full respect and faith in the past.

Behbudi was of the opinion that a nation can discuss socio-political issues on an equal footing with others only when it understands itself. That is why he paid special attention to history.

In general, Behbudi's work as a publicist is a very bright aspect of the writer's talent. He has written hundreds of articles throughout his life. He expressed his views on nation and homeland, society and morality in more articles and speeches. Some define his articles as 200, others as 300.

Not all of his articles have been identified. Importantly, he was a major political figure in Turkestan in the early twentieth century. All his views on the fate of the nation and the homeland were previously reflected in these articles. In this regard, his article "Hayrul umuri avsothu" ("The best of things is average"), published in the newspaper "Khurshid" (No. 6) on October 10, 1906, is noteworthy. For many years, this article was evaluated from the point of view of Soviet history and became a target for condemning Behbudi. The fact is that Behbudi had already in 1906 sharply rejected the socialist doctrine and Lenin's party, which was determined to implement it in Russia. He, like his teacher I. Gasprinsky, considered socialism to be violence, and social equality as

injustice. In the interest of the individual, he saw a great factor in the progress of the nation. The same belief led him to fight for the independence of Turkestan.

On April 16-23, 1917, Behbudi gave an exciting speech at a congress of 150 Turkestan Muslims in Tashkent. He called on the nation to renounce conflicts, to unite in the pursuit of a great goal, to become an alliance. For the same reason, he made it clear that "we are governed by the rule of colonialism."

On November 26 this year, the IV Extraordinary Congress of Muslims of the region began its work in Kokand. On the night of November 27, the "Autonomy of Turkestan" was declared. It was a serious and courageous step towards independence from the colony. His spiritual father was, without a doubt, Behbudi. However, it was treacherously suppressed by the Soviets. On February 19-20, the city was hit by the ball. 10,000 Turkestans were killed and 180 villages were set on fire.

Behbudi returns to Samarkand in agony. Unable to stay there, he comes to Tashkent. Turkestan is trying to negotiate with the leaders of the Russian Soviet government. Naturally, negotiations do not yield results. He knew that the path of the Soviets, which denied the nation, national development, was based on deception and violence. For this reason, he had already declared it in 1906 as contrary to reason and the Shari'ah.

Behbudi, whose dreams were shattered, set out in the spring of 1919, on March 25, in disarray, and was arrested in Shakhrisabz, and about two months later brought to Karshi and imprisoned. A few days later, on the orders of Uncle Karshi Togaybek, he was killed in the "royal garden" near the prison. The news of his assassination became known to the then capital Samarkand a year later. In April 1920, the whole of Turkestan mourned. In 1926-27, for 11 years, the city of Karshi was named after Behbudi. The literaryization of the writer's name was just a mask, his original image was kept secret from the people. As early as 1926, when the city of Karshi was named after him, a campaign was launched to condemn Jadidism as a counter-revolutionary, anti-Soviet movement.

In short, today the country, which Behbudi and others hold sacred, has become free and independent. The generations of independence they sacrificed their lives for. Those who sacrificed their lives for the independence of the nation and the homeland will live forever.

List of sources used:

[1] Aliev A: Mahmudkhoja Behbudi. -T .: Writer, 1994.

[2] Mahmudhoja Behbudi: Selected Works. Revised and supplemented 2nd edition. Tashkent: Spirituality, 1999.

[3] Haji Muin: Selected Works. Collector and publisher N.Namozova. - Tashkent: Spirituality, 2005.

[4] Qosimov B: <https://ziyouz.uz/ozbek-nasri/mahmudxoja-behbudiy/>

[5] Mahmudhoja Behbudi: Selected Works. Revised and supplemented 2nd edition. Tashkent: Spirituality, 1999.

[6] Aliev A: Mahmudhoja Behbudi. -T .: Writer, 1994.

[7] Mahmudhoja Behbudi: Selected Works. Revised and supplemented 2nd edition. Tashkent: Spirituality, 1999.

[8] Jadidism: the struggle for reform, renewal, independence and development.-T .: 1999.

[9] Qosimov B: <https://ziyouz.uz/ozbek-nasri/mahmudxoja-behbudiy/>

[10] National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. Volume 1